

TITLE: Rehabilitative and Assistive Robotics Research in Italy: The Fit4Medical Robotics Initiative

Description of the workshop proposal

Rehabilitative and assistive robots primarily aim to provide personal assistance with daily tasks and offer rehabilitative or pre-habilitation treatments to individuals at risk of frailty. Their main long-term goal is to enhance the quality of life and the quality of care perceived by citizens. These robots have the potential to assist individuals from childhood through to old age. Additionally, they support healthcare practitioners by monitoring people' conditions, thus facilitating and enhancing clinical assessments and rehabilitative interventions. This capability arises from the unique combination of features offered by robots: they are equipped with sensors and computational reasoning to understand and interpret environmental cues or people' intentions, and they have physical bodies to perform actions based on this reasoning. In recent years, research has been conducted in the fields of biomedical engineering, mechanics, control, materials, ethics, and law, as well as involving clinical and business experts, to provide evidence in the areas of **rehabilitative robotics, assistive robotics, and clinical assessment**. In this context, this workshop aims to foster discussion among robotics' developers, clinical experimenters and experts in the field of ethics and impact assessment starting from the experience of the Fit4Medical Robotics project. Its primary purpose is to discuss the lessons learned from the fields as well as open challenges and future directions of research, deployment, and widespread utilization of these technologies. Particular emphasis will be placed on discussing the state-of-the-art evidence of effectiveness and the need/significance of large-scale clinical trials, which will play a pivotal role in shaping the course of future investigations. The WS is organized to cover 3 aspects: rehabilitative robotics, socially assistive robotics and technology related to the assessment. Additionally, this workshop will propose a round table with experts to foster the discussion on synergies, barriers and limitations encountered that should be further analysed to promote the adoption of these machines in daily practice.

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Organizers: Laura Fiorini (University of Florence), Andrea Orlandini (CNR), Maura Casadio (University of Genoa)

Tentative Program and Invited Speaker

Introduction and user needs (20 min)

- Introduction and scientific objectives, Christian Cipriani, Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna

CONFIRMED

-"Clinical Translation and Innovation" Irene Aprile, Fondazione Don Gnocchi **CONFIRMED**

Fit4Med for Rehabilitation Robotics (30 min):

- “Robotic Platforms & Allied Digital technologies for assessment and rehabilitation” - Marco Controzzi, Scuola Superiore Sant’Anna, **CONFIRMED**

- “AI and Wearable Sensors for Health KPI”, Daniele Pucci, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, **CONFIRMED**

- “The Sixth Robotic Finger: From Engineering Design to Clinical Practice”, Gionata Salvietti, Università degli Studi di Siena, **CONFIRMED**

Fit4Med for Assistive Robotics (30 min):

- “Next Generation components for assistance” Fanny Ficuciello, Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II, **CONFIRMED**

- “Diversity-aware care robots” Antonio Sgorbissa, Università degli Studi di Genova **CONFIRMED**

- “Fostering Behavior Change through Cognitive Social Robotics”, Alessandro Umbrico, CNR-ISTC, **CONFIRMED**

Round Table with Speaker (30 min): in addition to the invited speaker other confirmed invited participants are: Lorenzo Molinari Tosatti, Marianna Semprini, Simona Crea, Fulvio Mastrogiovanni, Benedetto Allotta, Nicola Secciani, Manuel Catalano, Antonio Bicchi. *Alternatively, in case the WS must be within the 1.5 hour then we can leave 10 minutes to questions and open discussion.*

Each speaker will be encouraged to provide insights from the project highlighting successful applications of the described methodologies as well as present the current state of research and future perspectives in this broad field of study. The WS will offer an overview of research as well as a round-table discussing the state of the research on these topics as well as the open challenges related to sustainability and potential future Impact.

Expected number of participants: around 50 people

Target audience: people that work in the robotics community with a particular focus on assistive and rehabilitation robotics; doctors and physiotherapists; people who work in the artificial intelligence field; master and PhD students. The possible presence of exhibition stands in the Maker Faire may foster also the participation of a general audience (especially, students and young people). The workshop will take into account this opportunity and will try to dedicate specific attention also to specific dissemination actions in order to maximize its outreach.

Workshop documentation and impact on the robotic community: We plan to publish all the information of the WS on the web page of the event including the slides and the documentation presented by the speakers. We aim to publish a small report after the workshop including the most significant elements highlighted during the event. The whole I-RIM community will have the opportunity to access this information and take advantage of the insights pointed out and discussed during the WS.

Preferred Time: Friday afternoon or Saturday morning because of the availability of some speakers.